

Supplementary Material

Figure S1. Posterior density interval estimates of genotype effect on pup retrieval. **a,b**, latency to first visit and retrieval probability respectively. XX females are defined as the reference population and slope estimates are represented for XX* and X*Y females effects. Estimates are on the log (x+1) and logit scale (**a** and **b** respectively). Shaded areas represent 89% Highest Posterior Density intervals (HPD) and groups whose HPD intervals cross the vertical grey line are considered as not significantly different from the reference group (XX).

Figure S2. Visit latencies for females responding only. **a**, Estimates of first visit latency per genotype. Values are medians \pm 89% HPD intervals. Estimates are retrieved from a back-transformation of models' parameters. *Asterisk indicate significance of the genotype effect. **b**, Posterior density interval estimates of genotype effect. XX females are defined as the reference population and slope estimates are represented for XX* and X*Y female effects. Estimates are on the log (x+1) scale. Shaded areas represent 89% Highest Posterior Density intervals (HPD) and group whose HPD intervals cross the vertical grey line are considered as not significantly different from the reference group (XX). $n_{XX}=20$, $n_{XX^*}=29$, $n_{X^*Y}=31$.

Figure S3. The sex chromosome complement does not influence direct mother-pup interactions in the African pygmy mouse. Values are medians \pm 89% HPD intervals. Estimates are retrieved from a back-transformation of models' parameters. $n=25$ per genotype.

Figure S4. Posterior density interval estimates of the genotype effect on mother-pup interactions. **a**, grooming duration. **b**, crouching duration. **c**, huddling duration. **d**, pup displacement in the cage probability. XX females are defined as the reference population and slope estimates are represented for XX* and X*Y females effects. Estimates are on the log ($x+1$) (**a,b,c**) or logit scale (**d**). Shaded areas represent 89% Highest Posterior Density intervals (HPD) and group whose HPD intervals cross the vertical grey line are considered as not significantly different from the reference group (XX). $n=25$ per genotype.

Figure S5. Vasopressin neurons distribution across the PVN. Values are mean \pm s.e.m. We removed one X*Y female due to staining issues on few brain slices. Regions (1-5) are illustrated in Fig S7-S10. $n_{XX}=4$, $n_{XX^*}=4$, $n_{X^*Y}=2$, $n_{XY}=3$. Males tend to have greater vasopressin neurons in region 2 (early intermediate region) and X*Y females tend to have lower vasopressin neurons in region 1 (anterior region).

Figure S6. Oxytocin neurons distribution across the PVN. Values are mean \pm s.e.m. Regions (1-5) are illustrated in Fig S7-S10. $n_{XX}=5$, $n_{XX^*}=5$, $n_{X^*Y}=4$, $n_{XY}=4$. There is a tendency for a left skewed oxytocin distribution in XX females with a greater neuron number in anterior regions, while in intermediate regions for X*Y females and both regions for XX* and XY individuals. X*Y females tend to have a lower number of oxytocin neurons in region 1 and 5 in comparison to other individuals.

Figure S7. Oxytocin and vasopressin neurons' expression across the PVN in XX females. **a**, region 1 : anterior. **b,c**, regions 2 and 3 : intermediate. **d,e**, regions 4 and 5 : posterior.

Figure S8. Oxytocin and vasopressin neurons' expression across the PVN in XX* females. **a**, region 1 : anterior. **b,c**, regions 2 and 3 : intermediate. **d,e**, regions 4 and 5 : posterior.

Figure S9. Oxytocin and vasopressin neurons' expression across the PVN in X*Y females. **a**, region 1 : anterior. **b,c**, regions 2 and 3 : intermediate. **d,e**, regions 4 and 5 : posterior.

Figure S10. Oxytocin and vasopressin neurons' expression across the PVN in XY males. **a**, region 1 : anterior. **b,c**, regions 2 and 3 : intermediate. **d,e**, regions 4 and 5 : posterior.

	Latency to visit (s)		Retrieval probability	
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>
XX	156.5	94.5 –223.3	0.47	0.32 –0.63
XX*	112	71.5– 158.6	0.55	0.42 –0.70
X*Y	51.7	33.6– 73.8	0.87	0.77 –0.95
Contrasts	<i>ratio</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>	<i>Odd ratio</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>
XX / X*Y	2.97	1.57-4.65	0.14	0.03–0.30
XX / XX*	1.4	0.7-2.1	0.74	0.23–1.4
XX* / X*Y	2.1	1.09-3.31	0.19	0.04-0.4

Table S1. Median estimates and median-based contrast estimates for pup retrieval experiments. Contrast estimates with 89% HPD including 1 are considered as not significantly different. An odd-ratio above one (or near 0) indicates a higher (or lower) behavioural likelihood in the first group of the contrast, an odd-ratio around 1 indicates no group-effect. Probabilities and latencies (s) are retrieved using a back-transformation of the model parameters. $n_{XX}=31$, $n_{XX^*}=35$, $n_{X^*Y}=35$.

Genotype	Pup retrieval				Mother-pup interactions				
	<i>N</i>	Mean litter size ± sd	Visit response (%)	Retrieval response (%)	<i>N</i>	Carrying (%)	Grooming (%)	Crouching (%)	Huddling (%)
XX	31	3 ±1	20 (64.5)	15 (48.4)	25	19 (0.76)	20 (0.8)	23 (0.92)	18 (0.72)
XX*	35	3 ±1	29 (82.9)	19 (54.3)	25	17 (0.68)	22 (0.88)	22 (0.88)	21 (0.84)
X*Y	35	4 ±2	31 (88.6)	30 (85.7)	25	17 (0.68)	18 (0.72)	20 (0.8)	22 (0.88)

Table S2. Group sample sizes and proportions of individuals showing a response for pup retrieval and mother-pup interactions experiments. Mean litter sizes per genotype are represented for pup retrieval as the whole litter remained with mothers.

	Grooming Duration (s)		Crouching duration (s)		Huddling duration (s)		Pup displacement probability	
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>
XX	4.87	2.49-7.46	10.98	5.32-19	4.95	2.15-8	0.76	0.53-0.94
XX*	5.79	2.89-8.70	15.61	7.73-26.5	7.30	3.43-11.5	0.67	0.42-0.89
X*Y	3.18	1.36-4.99	7.89	3.34-13.2	7.33	3.63-11.7	0.68	0.43-0.9
Contrasts	<i>ratio</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>	<i>ratio</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>	<i>ratio</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>	<i>Odd ratio</i>	<i>HPD (89%)</i>
XX / X*Y	1.42	0.75-2.21	1.36	0.52-2.52	0.71	0.32-1.21	1.54	0.24-5.93
XX / XX*	0.87	0.44-1.33	0.71	0.27-1.34	0.71	0.32-1.2	1.58	0.25-6.37
XX*/ X*Y	1.64	0.86-2.57	1.88	0.66-3.43	1	0.42-1.62	0.96	0.12-3.47

Table S3. Median estimates and median-based contrast estimates for mother-pup interaction investigations Contrast estimates with 89% HPD including 1 are considered as not significantly different. An odd-ratio above one (or near 0) indicates a higher (or lower) behavioural likelihood in the first group of the contrast, an odd-ratio around 1 indicates no group-effect. Probabilities and durations (s) are retrieved using a back-transformation of the model parameters. n=25 per genotype.

Genotype	Nesting			Parental Care Strategy			
	<i>N</i>	Mean litter size	Females using the nestlet (%)	<i>N</i>	Mean litter size	Mean number of obs. / individual	Males killed or removed* (%)
XX	24	3 ±1	12 (50)	29	3 ±1	4 ± 2	7 (25.9)
XX*	28	3 ±1	16 (57.1)	39	3 ±1	4 ±1.5	7 (23.1)
X*Y	28	4 ±1	3 (10.7)	37	4 ±1	3 ± 2	16 (43.2)

Table S4. Descriptive statistics for nesting and parental care strategy experiments. * i.e., score of 1